

BBMRI-ERIC DIRECTORY USER MANUAL

MANUAL FOR USERS

Version 3.0.2

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INTRODUCTION

The Directory provides a central listing of biobanks and their collections in the BBMRI-ERIC member states. For researchers, the Directory offers a means of finding samples and data, while for biobanks it offers a platform to share the existence of their holdings and services and to connect with researchers interested in them.

The Directory (Holub 2016) is one of the services offered by BBMRI-ERIC Common Services for IT (CS-IT) to the global biobank community and was created in collaboration with the BBMRI National Nodes and partners.

The screenshot displays the BBMRI-ERIC Directory landing page. At the top, there is a navigation bar with the BBMRI-ERIC logo and links for Home, Background, Map of Biobanks, and Help, along with a Sign in button. Below the navigation bar is a search area with a search input field, a clear button (x), and a Request button with a counter (0). Underneath the search area are several filter buttons: Diagnosis available, Countries, Collection type, Categories, Material type, Services type, Quality labels, Network, Data category, and a checkbox for Available to commercial use. The search results section shows: Organisations: 472, Collections: 3369, and Services: 0. A pagination control shows 1 - 12 of 472. Two biobank profiles are displayed: 1. "Bruno Boerci" Biobank - ICS Maugeri: Shows 7 collections available. The first collection is "Biobanca per la ricerca Bruno Boerci" with details: Available: 2000 samples, Type: Disease specific, Materials: Tissue (frozen), Plasma, Peripheral blood cells, Tissue (paraffin preserved), Whole Blood. The second collection is "Breast Cancer Collection" with details: Type: Disease specific, Sample collection, Hospital, Cohort. 2. A Coruña Biobank: Shows "This biobank has no collections yet."

Figure 1- Directory Landing Page

TERMINOLOGY

In the Directory and in this document, we make a distinction between a biobank as an organisation and the collections of a biobank. Where we use the term “biobank”, we are referring to the organisation, and where we use the term “collection”, we are referring to the samples and data held by the biobank. These definitions of “biobank” and “collection” are in line with the MIABIS 2.0 Core community standard (Merino-Martinez 2016).

NAVIGATING THE DIRECTORY

Overview

The Directory is a broad catalogue of biobanks with their samples and data at the collection level. You can browse and filter by country, sample type, quality marks and more.

In the directory, you can see the cards (1). Each card represents a biobank. On a biobank’s card, you can see information about the biobank and a list of its available collections.

Figure 2- The biobanks represented as cards

Search for a Biobank/Collection or Sample

You can use the search option (2). In the search bar, you can search for your desired biobank, by searching for the biobank name, collection name, or the diagnosis. For example, you can type Graz, if you are looking for the Graz biobank. You can see that the result shows you the Biobank Graz card.

Figure 3- The search bar and the filters

Or you can use the filters (3) to narrow down the results. For example, you can filter by diagnosis or a specific country. You can filter material type, or search for biobanks with a specific quality label. For example, if you were interested in seeing all biobanks with birth cohort collections, you would navigate to “Collection Types” and check the box for “Birth cohort”, and then on the right a table with biobanks with birth cohort collections would appear.

On the left top corner (4) you can see the number of results specified by the number of organisations, number of collections and subcollections.

If you are not interested in the filters, or you would like to search for different collections, you can click on “Clear all filters” (5) to reset all the filters.

Figure 4- Displaying the number of results specified by the number of organisations, number of collections and subcollections and “Clear all filters” options.

The Biobank Cards

Each card represents a biobank. On a biobank's card, you can see a list of available collections. If there are several collections available on this card, you can see them by scrolling down inside the card.

Figure 5- Example of a biobank card

By clicking on the tab for “Services” (6), a list of available biobank services instead of collections is displayed. By clicking on the tab for “Organisation” (7), you can access more information about the Biobank, such as Collection types and Juridical person. If you need more details about the biobank, you can always click on “More details” (8) to go to the Biobank page. Click on the “Collections” tab to view the collections again. You can also view more details about each collection of the biobank by clicking on “More details” (9). This will open the collections page.

Figure 6- Biobank cards displaying the information on different tabs: collections, services and additional information on the biobank organisation.

Biobank/Collection Quality Label

In some biobank cards you may see a green icon (10) which indicates that the biobank has a quality label. By hovering over it you can see the quality label type. Also, the quality label of each collection is specified in its specifications. When you hover over the blue question mark (11) you can see the quality label type of the collection.

Figure 7- Biobank and collection quality label icon and information.

To see more detailed information on a specific biobank, click the name of the biobank at the top of the card and you will be taken to a page with additional information on the biobank. For more information on a collection, click on the collection name and you will be taken to a page with additional information on the collection. To go back to the search page, click “Back to the catalogue” at the top of the page.

The top menu

All Directory pages are directly accessible from the navigation bar at the top of each page.

Figure 8- Navigation bar located at the top of each page

Navigation bar items:

- **BBMRI-ERIC logo or “Home”** on the left of the navigation bar will take you to the Directory landing page.
- **“Background”** gives a short description of the Directory and its target audience.
- **“Map of Biobanks”** shows all locations of biobanks on a map of Europe.
- **“Help”** provides access to the Directory User Manual and Data Managers Manual documents.
- **“Sign in”** is for the use of Directory administrators and data managers only.

Request Cart

When you find the collections you are interested in, you can proceed to request them. You can select a collection by checking the box next to the collection name (12). You can also select several collections by checking the box at the top of the collection list (13). At any time, you can have an overview of the selected collections on the request cart by clicking on the “Request”-button (14) in the top right corner.

Since the Directory contains thousands of collections you might first need to limit the results by searching for relevant terms. For example, if you were looking for a specific disease you could use the Diagnosis filter and select the specific ICD-10 diagnosis code to limit the results to biobanks that have indicated that they have samples related to that diagnosis.

BBMRI-ERIC® Home Background Map of Biobanks Help Sign in

Search x

Select all collections 1000 Request 1

Diagnosis available Countries 1 Collection type Categories Material type

Services type Quality labels Network Data category Available to commercial use

Clear all filters

Search results

Organisations: 4

Collections: 1000

Services: 0

Biobank Graz ✓

Because you searched for: Austria

Collections Services Organisation

612 collections found

Bio-UV 2017: Photo(chemo)therapy in skin diseases

Available: 4111 samples

Type: Disease specific, Sample collection, Hospital, Cohort, Longitudinal

Biobank Innsbruck ✓

Because you searched for: Austria

Collections Services Organisation 13

44 collections found

HumGen DB

Available: 33298 samples

Type: Other, Sample collection

Materials: Other, DNA, Whole Blood

More details

Figure 9- Adding collections to the Request Cart

USING THE NEGOTIATOR

The “Negotiator” function enables a researcher interested in specific samples or data to start a conversation with one or more biobanks, during which he/she can refine the query and eventually request samples or data. To start a conversation, click the “Request” button (13) at the top of the screen showing your search results. View your selected collections one more time, and if you are happy with your selection you can proceed by clicking on the “Send to the Negotiator” button which will redirect you to the negotiator to fill out a request form.

FINAL NOTE

BBMRI-ERIC encourages all biobanks in member states to register in the Directory. Please contact the BBMRI-ERIC helpdesk with any questions, at directory@helpdesk.bbmri-eric.eu.

REFERENCES

1. Merino-Martinez Roxana, Norlin Loreana, van Enckevort David, Anton Gabriele, Schuffenhauer Simone, Silander Kaisa, Mook Linda, Holub Petr, Bild Raffael, Swertz Morris, and Litton Jan- Eric. Biopreservation and Biobanking. August 2016, 14(4): 298-306.
<https://doi.org/10.1089/bio.2015.0070>
2. Holub Petr, Swertz Morris, Reihns Robert, van Enckevort David, Müller Heimo, and Litton Jan- Eric. Biopreservation and Biobanking. December 2016, 14(6): 559-562.
<https://doi.org/10.1089/bio.2016.0088>

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